

Revisiting the Use of Translation in L2 Classrooms¹

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Introduction

There is a common perception among English teachers that the use of mother tongue and L1-based activities, such as translation, should be avoided in L2 classrooms. This idea is often the result of the views that perceive maximum exposure to L2 as a condition for the learning of the foreign language (Celik, 2008).

The present paper suggests that limited and judicious use of translation from and into the mother tongue in English classrooms can assist in the teaching and learning process (Sharma, 2006) and can improve the learners' skills, namely writing.

English-only

Many people in the language teaching community still discourage or even ban the use of the mother tongue in their classrooms because they see it as a hindrance. This negative attitude towards the inclusion of L1 in L2 programs owes its origins to some theoretical frameworks, namely the Audio-Lingual and the Communicative Methods which label the use of the learner's first language as counter-productive (Sharma, 2006).

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Although such methodologies have originated in English-speaking settings and were meant to meet the needs of multinational language classes where different linguistic backgrounds and cultures can be found, some teachers of English still, unrealistically, try to implement policies that were *not* developed by them nor for their students, overlooking the differences that exist between multilingual and monolingual contexts (Murakami, 2001, as cited in Celik, 2008).

Proponents of English-only believe that foreign language learners can acquire a language “by immersion” (Weschler, 1997). However, researchers who differentiate between *acquisition* and *learning*, suggest that while the former requires immersion in the target language environment, the latter normally takes place in monolingual settings where the foreign language is *not* the mother tongue (Atkinson, 1987, as cited in Celik, 2008), and therefore, such learning does not entail full exposure to L2 nor does it exclude the use of L1.

In fact, EFL teachers find the prohibition of L1 in L2 classrooms to be both impossible and impractical (Nunan and Lamb, 1996; Macaro, 1997; DOrnyei and Kormos, 1998; as cited in Sharma, 2006). Brookes-Lewis (2009, as cited in Debreli & Oyman, 2016) points out that the inclusion of the mother tongue in EFL classrooms is inevitable since many learners use it to compensate for their deficiencies in the target language.

Thou shalt not translate

Several foreign language teachers still have reservations about using translation from and into the first language in their classrooms. They object to it because they associate it with the obsolete Grammar Translation Method that “abstracted language from its communicative function” (Weschler, 1997; Kayaoğlu, 2012). For them, allowing the use of translation would automatically result in inappropriate transfer from the mother tongue to the target language (Jadallah & Hasan, 2010; Littlewood & Yu, 2011, as cited in Debreli & Oyman, 2016).

However, attitude towards translation in language classes has seen vast changes following the recognition that “mental translation is virtually unavoidable” (Cohen, 1996, as cited in Weschler, 1997), and that some learners *do* resort to their L1 to improve their FL learning experience (Odlin, 1989; James, 1998; Cook, 2000; Gill, 2003; as cited in Jadallah & Hasan, 2010).

In fact, research has demonstrated that since “Translation/transfer is a natural phenomenon and an inevitable part of second language acquisition..., regardless of whether or not the teacher offers 'permits' of translation” (Harbord, 1992, as cited in Sharma, 2006), learners have a “natural tendency” (Weschler, 1997) to “translate silently” (Titford, 1985, as cited in Sharma, 2006).

Preventing learners from developing this natural translation ability can do more harm than good since transfer between L1 and L2 will take place anyway. It is argued that

deliberately exposing students to differences and similarities of the two languages can help increase communicative competence (Duff, 1989, as cited in Ferrer, 2005). Researchers (Atkinson, 1993; Cole, 1998; Macaro, 2001, as cited in Celik, 2008; Miles, 2004; Elridge, 1996; Voicu, 2012; Afzal, 2013; Spahiu, 2013, as cited in Debreli & Oyman, 2016) report that if used “appropriately and necessarily”, the mother tongue, and therefore translation, can be employed as an important pedagogical tool in language classes (Kayaoğlu, 2012).

Translation as a teaching tool

EFL classrooms cannot and should not serve as translator training platforms. However, a carefully-planned inclusion of translation in ELT programs can only be of benefit to the students. L1-based language teaching methods such as the New Concurrent Method (Faltis, 1990, as cited in Jadallah & Hasan, 2010) believe that contrastive analysis of the two languages help learners “predict and address potential problems of interference” (Richards, 1986; Meiring & Norman, 2002; Butzkamm, 2003, as cited in Weschler, 1997; Celik, 2008). Duff (1989, as cited in Ferrer, 2005) argues that “if properly designed, translation activities can be employed to enhance the four skills and develop accuracy, clarity and flexibility.”

Although the purpose of translation in the language classroom is not to train professionals (Ferrer, 2005), L2 teachers are advised to resort to Translation Studies to inform their practice. According to Weschler (1997), the focus of translation has to be changed from the linguistic (i.e. the word or structure) to the functional (i.e. translation units). In fact, if

redefined as communication-oriented activity, translation can help learners avoid erroneous L1-L2 transfer by shedding light on challenging aspects that might lack immediate equivalents in the target language, namely collocation and connotation (Kavaliauskienė, 2009).

Some believe (see for example Snell- Hornby, 1985; Thiel, 1985; Marsh, 1987, as cited in Carreres, 2006) that learners cannot tackle translation productively before acquiring a significant proficiency level. This is largely true. However, this does not mean that translation should be left out at any stage of learning. In fact, translation offers a number of methods ranging from the hyper-literal to the communicative (Carreres, 2006), allowing language teachers to cater to their students, regardless of their levels.

Taking into account their unique situations, individual teachers can decide for themselves when and how to use translation. Generally, the use of L1, and therefore of translation, is associated with pre-writing brainstorming (Weschler, 1997), explicating confusing English structures, disambiguating certain ambiguous sentences (Mukattash, 2003, as cited in Jadallah & Hasan, 2010), illustrating a lesson's objectives, checking comprehension, discussing the main themes after reading, and articulating the classroom rules and requirements at the beginning of each semester (Willis, 1998, as cited in Celik, 2008). Other uses of the mother tongue take place when highlighting cultural similarities and differences (Jadallah & Hasan, 2010), teaching certain complex and complicated concepts and ideas in a language, and providing a swift and clear-cut synonym or

paraphrase of a complicated concept or an utterance (Duff, 1989; Atkinson, 1993, as cited in Celik, 2008).

It is argued that even at the advanced level, the majority of L2 learners will always think in their L1 (Weschler, 1997), and will therefore keep mentally translating (Mahmoud, 2006, as cited in Kavaliauskienė, 2009) because “one’s mother tongue is their language of thought and cognition, and it is a much-needed tool for stimulating memory and semantic processing” (Celik, 2008). This fact should make foreign language teachers focus more on using L1 in activities that require thinking, especially writing, since translation in such situations can be very promising for language learners (Freidlander, 1990; Kobayashi & Rinnert, 1992; Antón & DiCamilla, 1998, as cited in Celik, 2008).

The above uses of L2 through translation should not be regarded as “an open invitation to indiscriminate use of L1” (Meiring & Norman, 2002, as cited in Celik, 2008). Indeed, there are certain situations and types of activities when use of the mother tongue is unproductive, namely listening and speaking (Chambers, 1991; Cole, 1998, as cited in Celik, 2008).

Conclusion

Learner-centered language teaching urges researchers and practitioners to investigate anything that might be of assistance to students’ learning (Ferrer, 2005). In this regard, this paper reflects upon the use of translation in the foreign language classroom since the judicious use of L1 in L2 settings may contribute to developing learners’ skills (Jadallah

& Hasan, 2010), and more importantly, to battling the fear of what some refer to as “linguistic imperialism” (Phillipson, 1992; Canagarajah, 1999, as cited in Celik, 2008).

Although there is enough evidence to suggest that translation has an important role to play in language teaching, more empirical research is needed.

References

- Carreres, A. (2006). Strange bedfellows: Translation and Language teaching. The teaching of Translation into L2 in modern languages degree; uses and limitations. *Cambridge University Press*, 1-21. Retrieved from: <http://www.cttic.org/mission.asp>
- Celik, S. (2008). Opening the door: An examination of mother tongue use in foreign language classrooms. *Hacettepe University Journal of Education*, 34(34). Retrieved from: <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ802519>
- Debreli, E., & Oyman, N. (2016). Students' preferences on the use of mother tongue in English as a foreign language classrooms: Is it the time to re-examine English-only policies? *English Language Teaching*, 9(1), 148. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/elt.v9n1p148>
- Ferrer, V. (2005). The mother tongue in the classroom: Cross-linguistic comparisons, noticing and explicit knowledge. Retrieved from: <http://www.teachenglishworldwide.com>
- Jadallah, M., & Hasan, F. (2010, October). A review of some new trends in using L1 in the EFL classroom. Paper presented at National conference on improving TEFL methods & practices at Palestinian universities. Retrieved from: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/>
- Kavaliauskienė, G. (2009). Role of mother tongue in learning English for specific purposes. *ESP world*, 8(1), 2-8. . Retrieved from: <http://www.esp-world.info>

- Kayaoğlu, M. N. (2012). The use of mother tongue in foreign language teaching from teachers' practice and perspective. *Pamukkale Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 32(2), 25-35.
- Miles, R. (2004). *Evaluating the use of L1 in the English language classroom* (Master's thesis, University of Birmingham, UK). Retrieved from: <https://www.birmingham.ac.uk>
- Sert, O. (2005). The Functions of code-switching in ELT classrooms. *The Internet TESL Journal*, 11(8). Retrieved from: <http://iteslj.org/>
- Sharma, K. (2006). Mother tongue use in English classroom. *Journal of NELTA*, 11(1-2), 80-87. Retrieved from: <http://www.nelta.org.np>
- Weschler, R. (1997). Uses of Japanese in the English classroom: Introducing the Functional-Translation Method. *Kyoritsu Women's University Department of International Studies Journal*, 12, 87-110. Retrieved from: <https://eric.ed.gov/>